

RESPONSE PAPER

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INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below)

1. The Basic of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019,1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-36)
5. Sample corrections to papers (EUCLID 2019,36-43)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2019,44-55)
7. Latin Abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56-59)

METHODES AND TECHNIQUES FOR ACADEMIC PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one reminds me of the Latin say "mens sana in corpore sano" to mean that a saint spirit stays within a saint body. Good content needs a well-presented book, essay, or dissertation, because the form always impacts on the content. Radio and television select smart presenters with clear voices to attract wide audience and advertisers. The well-dressed books, essays, and dissertations attract readers and earn their authors' recognition contrary to those mal-presented that end up dumped.

However, the coursepack provides required methods, tools, and techniques for new students to write an academic and professional paper in an international context. It also brings out supporting documents and examples from reliable sources detailed in eight chapters. As a new student, the coursepack and the associated video document offer me essential knowledge and clear guidance to shape my writing style to be adapted to the international academic and professional level. The skills and knowledge I will gain from

the course, will contribute to my success throughout this long journey of studying the "Diplomacy and International Affairs" program at Euclid University.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

The "Essay Writing Basics" is the first chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one. It delivers requirements for a good essay, and provides process and methods to follow from starting the essay up to its handing in. "The essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence" (EUCLID 2019, 1); and this requires convincing and factual arguments collected and gained through intensive and extensive reading, researching, thinking, and writing. The latter earn a writer to develop and answer to an essay question or task using a thesis supported by argument, evidence, and relevant examples from consulted texts.

When I was sub-editor of the Rwanda government newspaper "Imvaho- nshya" (new newspaper) in 2004, I always reminded journalists that a good article responds clearly to the curiosity of the audience by finding answers to "who, what, when, where, how, and why" questions. As a journalist needs a reliable source to present journalistic and accurate information, a paper writer relies on other written sources to back his or her thesis using information and knowledge gained from carried out researches. I agree with the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one on the structure of an international academic and professional paper, composed of an introduction, body, and conclusion. "An introduction moves from general to specific; and the body comprises of paragraphs developing discussion, evidence, and examples supported by knowledge from read-materials. The conclusion moves from the specific to the general including a final and broad statement" (EUCLID 2019, 3).

EUCLID did not bring out the difference between an essay and other related writing papers mentioned throughout this coursepack (e.g. term papers and dissertations). The definition of an essay and its differences with other academic papers would contribute to avoid confusion due to some similarities. In *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, 8th Edition*, Hornby et al. define an essay as "a short piece of writing by a student as part of a course of study or a short piece of writing on a particular subject, written in order to be published" (2010, 457). A dissertation is "a long piece of writing on a particular subject, especially one written for a university degree" (Hornby et al. 2010, 423).

However, the lack of essay definition and differences with other papers does not impact negatively on the coursepack objective of offering the basics of proper English writing. It details methods, techniques, and requirements, which offer sufficient baggage to students newly embark on following the Euclid University programs.

3) PLAGIARISM, AN INTELLECTUAL OFFENSE

Plagiarism is defined as a “fact of using information without giving credit to the author of its source; or when someone writes a paper on your behalf and then put your name as if it is your own product” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Even if EUCLID qualifies plagiarism as wrong and unethical or an act of serious offense, its definition seems light compared to others. The latter define plagiarism as an act of fraud as it involves both stealing and lying about someone else's work. In its article “*what is plagiarism?*” published in May 2017, Plagiarism.org emphasizes the definition of Merriam Webster online dictionary. The latter highlights that to plagiarize means "to steal and pass off the ideas or words of another as one's own, to use another's production without crediting the source, to commit literary theft; to present as new and original an idea or product derived from an existing source" (plagiarism.org 2017).

Though information is for public use, both author and source deserve to be credited as the owner of that intellectual product. Information is the property of its author and any user has to acknowledge the source and respect author's intellectual rights. Rwanda property policy defines intellectual rights as: "assets resulted from human intellectual creative activity as intellectual property namely inventions, trademarks, designs, literary and artistic works, layout designs of integrated circuits, and trade secrets" (Republic of Rwanda, Ministry of Trade 2018, 5). EUCLID invites paper writers to avoid plagiarism citing in-text or listing works cited through quotations, paraphrases, footnotes, references, and bibliography.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

A paper writer starts his work by stating the main thesis of the paper in the opening paragraph. This part serves as an introduction that invites readers to have a general idea on the topic before its development. EUCLID emphasis that " your writing should care for readers' attention on the ideas you wish to express, not on the words you have chosen to express those ideas" (14). Short sentences, paragraphs, simple language and clear style are recommended in the development of the topic.

When I was in secondary school, I had a habit of resorting to complicated vocabularies borrowed from Latin for my composition work to impress my teacher. But, contrary to my intention, I ended up annoying him and obtaining unexpected results. Unclear style and complicated language lead to communication failure and affect information transmission. Journalism and communication teachers remind students that a good journalist is that who manages to transmit comprehensible information to the audience through simple language and clear style.

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH DIFFERENCES

EUCLID highlights that "American and British English are more similar than different, especially with educated and scientific English, even if standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBA) have some spelling and pronunciation differences" (2019, 28). The issue of English pronunciation and spelling is general. It is a problem to know who really speaks well and everyone, especially in Africa, pronounces on his or her way. I may be even right if I confirm that, contrary to other languages such as French, English has not universal standard pronunciation. English is spoken differently depending on the environment, and It happens that two English speakers fail to understand each other especially in Africa where English pronunciation is influenced by local languages.

However, the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one, apart from highlighting these differences and causes, addresses some concerns by availing basics of proper English. It also brings out requirements and techniques associated with writing academic papers in an international context.

6) CHICAGO STYLE

Dr. Abel Scribe describes Chicago style as " the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and Kate Turabian Manuel for writers of term papers, theses, and dissertations" (EUCLID 2019, 44). Chapter eight of the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one highlights style, page formatting, and end/footnotes required for a good paper.

This chapter does not only teach but also correct because it reveals mistakes I have committed unconsciously in my writings. The outlined guidance for a paper writer shows that a well-written paper does not only require impeccable content but also adequate form because the way the paper looks, has an impact. A presentable paper with well-aligned and spaced words adapted to the methods detailed in Turabian Manual for writers, impacts positively on its content. In the sub-heading "Chicago Page Formats," it is indicated that: "Turabian Manual for writers is the official guide to applying Chicago Style to term papers, theses, and dissertations; because the Chicago Manual of style focus on book publishing and has few instructions to offer for formatting papers" (EUCLID 2019, 49).

7) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Chapter seven of the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one consists of a sample of corrections to papers. However, the corrector's comments and observations focused only on content mistakes and exempted the writer from form mistakes. The author did not follow methods provided by Turabian's Manual for Writers which is an official guide to applying Chicago style. Moreover, the author did not consider the applied rules for indent applied

to all paragraphs, headings, and sub-headings. Turabian's Manual for Writers recommends indenting paragraphs on one-half inch to make any paper easy to read.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

When I was studying Latin in secondary schools, I regretted losing my time studying such a complicated and no longer spoken language. My view changed later when I was in secondary after meeting many Latin words in different courses especially law. Expressions such as "grosso modo" (in brief), "sine qua non" (condition), "statu quo" (current status), "sine die" (without date) remain frequent in ordinary communication. Etymology studies have also shown that many words have Latin origins.

However, Latin may be unspoken but is still alive through its words still used in other languages. Chapter nine details Latin abbreviations and expressions still used in English, especially in academic writing and publications. Other Latin words like "AM" (ante meridiem and "PM "(post meridiem) have become unavoidable in human daily communication because they are used everywhere as time format (EUCLID 2019, 56-57). The "A-C" (ante Christum natum) which means before Jesus Christ birth or "P.C" (post Christum natum) to mean after Jesus birth, are commonly used to determine the period of ancient events

9) CONCLUSION

As a non-native of English speaker country and a new student at Euclid University, it took me a lot of efforts to comprehend technical terms and words used across the ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack period one. Using Zotero, Grammarly premium and the application of Turabian's style, are challengers for any new user. But, as it is said that "where there is a will there is a way," my determination to pursue the "Master's in Diplomacy and International Affairs (MDIA)" program will facilitate to overcome all defies.

Despite linguistic challenges, the course is helpful to whoever newly embarks on advanced academic life at Euclid University. The ACA-401/ACA-401D period one revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma serves as my starting point to comprehend required methods and techniques to produce an academic paper. The reading of this coursepack and accompanying documents (videos) did not only shape my ability in academic paper writing, but also contributed to the improvement of my English level through acquired new vocabularies.

REFERENCES

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